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Research Article

**DETERMINING THE EFFECT OF AGING ON BURDEN OF
DISEASES**Dr Zaka Ullah, Dr Muhammad Afzal Khan, Dr Ahmad Ali
Jinnah Hospital Lahore**Article Received:** February 2020**Accepted:** March 2020**Published:** April 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: In this study, we presented a theoretical model to measure aging rate in Vietnam, quantitatively measuring the effect of aging rate on disease patterns in each country and explaining how these effects were obtained. The purpose of this study was to investigate how disease burden varies according to the level of medical infrastructure and changes in aging index using aging data and WHO disease burden data

Methods: In this study, health data on global disease burden of elderly people was analyzed from 2016 to 2019. The difference model (DID) was used to analyze the effects of aging.

Results: The burden of the disease increased over time, especially in the middle-aged population. In the event of loss of life due to premature death, the number of people in middle and old age has increased significantly. When we study the econometric model after checking the relevant factors, there has been a significant increase in the number of fatalities due to illness and premature death. On the other hand, the piles group at the aging level had a significant positive impact on the year life lost (YLL). As an important variable that shows the effect of a double age difference, the interaction effect did not affect the disability-adjusted year of life (DALY), but showed a significant positive effect on year life lost.

Conclusion: The loss of life due to the death of older people is higher than that of older people. Therefore, the impact of population aging on medical resources and future medical spending should take into account changes in the population structure, disease burden by age group, and the interaction of these two incremental factors.

Keywords: aging, disease burden, difference of differences.

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INTRODUCTION:

58.2% of respondents (n = 2549) suffer from chronic illness above 65 years of age, which confirms the prediction of the frequency of chronic diseases among older people. This increase in the prevalence of chronic diseases can accelerate due to the aging of the population. In Vietnam, aging was faster than in other countries. There was an eight-year difference between the average life expectancy (81 years) and the life expectancy adjusted for disability (73 years). Since seniors are an unprecedented part of the Vietnamese population, the community should pay more attention to the health of the elderly than focus on changes in the structure of the population with a high life expectancy^{1,2}. Increase in the elderly population.

What factors influenced the individual's health? Factors with a significant impact on health can generally be divided into demographic, socioeconomic, lifestyle and social factors³. These factors can also be classified as internal factors (such as perceptions of personality deterioration and physical performance) and external factors (such as loss of social status by retirement, changes in the economic level and changes in the regional environment)⁴.

Many researchers focus particularly on the socioeconomic levels of individuals who classify the social class by occupation, level of education, and income. These studies confirmed that there are differences in mortality and morbidity among social classes that shed light on the importance of socioeconomic factors⁵.

Work status can also affect health. Compared to ordinary employees, involuntary normal employees had low job and life satisfaction, which could have a negative impact on the overall quality of life, including health⁶. Working hours also affected employees' health. Long working hours had a detrimental effect on employees' health. Abnormal employees had more hours of work than ordinary employees. Therefore, they were not able to ask for timely treatment, which causes stress at work and ultimately has a negative impact on their health⁷.

The aging of the population was known as an important factor contributing to the increase in medical expenses, as medical expenses per capita were higher than in other age groups. Vietnam is experiencing unprecedented aging.

However, previous studies have shown that non-demographic causes account for a greater proportion of the increase in medical expenses, as opposed to the aging population⁸. The demographic index resulting from the increase in medical expenses in Vietnam was reported as 40%, 13.8%.

Although population aging is a possible two-sided factor that increases and suppresses medical expenses, few studies have used longitudinal data to confirm that the importance of ante-mortem costs has changed over time.

Therefore, the purpose of this study was to present and discuss a theoretical model for measuring the aging rate in Vietnam measuring the impact of aging rates on disease patterns and explaining these effects. WHO aging data and disease burden were used to analyze differences in disease burden depending on changes based on the level of medical infrastructure (GDP, medical technology, medical aid) in the aging indicator using a quasi-experimental model known as DID. By measuring the impact of aging on disease burden, and by checking the differences in health and economic conditions in countries with longitudinal data, this study attempted to analyze the pure impact of aging.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The disease burden data were used in this study. The Health department selects key statistics from a variety of areas, including health, every year and asks 34 member states to provide them. This index, also known as 'health data', covered health status, medical and health resources, and medical and health costs. In particular, these data contain information that can be used to directly and indirectly estimate the level of human and material resources related to medicine. Therefore, these data will be useful for checking the level of a particular country or health policy to measure the impact of aging on a country's disease model. In addition, Vietnam health system provided information on the population aged 65 and older in 5-year units that enable an analysis of aging indicators in each country. The purpose of this study was to compare changes in disease burden versus changes in the aging rate as an international standard. Therefore, the aging rate was calculated. In addition, the incidence load was distinguished in adults at an early age (65–69 years) and in middle and late age (70 years and older).

In this study, a difference model (DID) was used to analyze the effects of aging. The DID model was a semi-experimental model that allows comparison of pre-test and post-test states. The pure effect of aging was determined by confirming the difference in the rate of aging between control groups with different disease loads.

Based on previous research on variables affecting disease burden, the following variables were used as control variables: gross domestic product (GDP), total medical expenditure of the population, and expenditure on public health insurance. These variables were used to control social, medical and

beneficial infrastructure, respectively. With more infrastructure qualifications, the costs of medical

services and social assistance will be higher (Table 1).

Table 1: Description of variables

Variables	Description	
Dependent variable	DALY	Lost year due to diseases + Lost year due to early death
	YLL	Lost year due to early death
Independent variable	Dummy of years	2016=0, 2019=1
	Dummy of group	Early old age (year 65~69) =0 Mid and late old age (over 70 years old) =1
	Interaction variable	Interaction between year dummy and group dummy

RESULTS

DALY's height was higher than YLL, and the increase in the group of older to medium and late people was higher than in the group of older people. However, the differences in DALY in terms of aging or GDP were not significant. The disease burden in middle-aged adults is higher in countries with lower GDP than in older adults, while YLL is higher in middle-aged adults than in older countries. GDP

Table 2: Difference in Difference of aging effect on burden of diseases

		DALY		YLL	
		b	beta	b	beta
Constant		431.85	**	214.79	**
Control variable	GDP	314.52	0.064	114.27	217.3
	Total health expenditure	419.14	0.021		0.217
Dependent variable	Year(A) Group(B)	31.54	.124**	86.66	.214**
		198.71	.007	168.29	0.231*
	AXB	107.22	0.076	98.17	0.115*
	Public insurance expenditure	-98.47	-0.145**	-107.38	-0.004*
Model fit	F/ χ^2	26.947**		38.947**	
	R square	0.317		0.638	

There were no significant differences in AVAD or YLL in terms of aging or total cost of treatment. However, DALY is higher among those in countries with low public health insurance costs, while DALY is highest among middle-aged and late adults in countries with low public health insurance costs.

Table 2 shows the results of DID regression analysis for differences in aging levels. In the analysis model with dependent variables such as DALY and YLL, DALY was positive and YLL was negative. This showed that even after controlling other variables, the number of deaths due to illness was significantly reduced compared to the past. Meanwhile, an imaginary group of aging levels had a significant positive effect on YLL. The term interaction is an important variable that shows the effects of DID level aging. In addition, although it did not affect DALY, it had significant positive effects on YLL. This showed that YLL increased significantly with increasing levels of aging.

Regarding control variables, there was no significant difference in DALY or DPA in terms of GDP or total medical expenditure. However, DALY and YLL have fallen significantly with the increase in public spending on health insurance.

DISCUSSION:

This study examined the impact of aging levels on disease burden using health data and examined changes in disease burden.

The burden of the disease increased with time, with a more pronounced increase in adults from young to late age (65-69 years). The increase in YLL due to premature death is higher in middle and late older people than in older people⁹. In other words, the disease burden of the elderly has increased over time, and the increase in disease burden is greater in the elderly population¹⁰. When the econometric model was used after checking the appropriate

variables, the results showed that YLL disease and YLL increased significantly due to premature death¹¹. Meanwhile, an imaginary group of aging levels had a significant positive effect on YLL. The term interaction, which is an important variable showing the effects of DID level aging, had a significant positive effect on YLL, although it did not affect DALY¹². This showed that YLL increased significantly with increasing levels of aging.

We use GDP and medical expenses as control variables to control the level of medical technology in the country and the desire to seek treatment for human diseases¹³. We also use the costs of public health insurance as a control variable, because access to medical facilities can also affect the purpose of treatment. The results of the analysis showed that YLL due to premature aging increases with increasing levels of aging. This suggests that an increase in YLL leads to an increase in disease burden¹⁴.

As the disease developed, it was easy for middle-aged and late adults to develop other co-morbidities because of the slow recovery and immunodeficiency states that increase the burden of morbidity compared to older adults. In the elderly group, the disease load, especially YLL, was about three times higher than the effect on the total disease load. After examining the moderate effects of aging based on the time of interaction, the results showed that aging has a significant effect on stress disease, especially YLL due to death¹⁵.

If the increase in YLL due to death is relatively higher in older people compared to young people, the interaction between these two factors should be considered when determining changes in population structure, disease burden by age group, and the effects of population aging on future medical resources or medical expenses. In addition, policies should be developed that help stabilize the burden of morbidity among older people, based on measuring the exact effects of aging.

CONCLUSION:

The burden of the disease increased over time, with a more pronounced increase in the elderly population from mid to late. The increase in YLL due to premature death is higher in the middle-aged and late-adult population than in the elderly population. In other words, the disease burden in older people has increased over time, and the increase in disease burden is higher in the elderly population. Analyzed using an econometric model that controls related variables, it showed that YLL increased significantly due to premature death.

REFERENCES:

1. Melaku, Yohannes Adama, Andre Renzaho, Tiffany K. Gill, Anne W. Taylor, Eleonora Dal Grande, Barbora de Courten, Estifanos Baye et al. "Burden and trend of diet-related non-communicable diseases in Australia and comparison with 34 OECD countries, 1990–2015: Findings from the Global Burden of Disease Study 2015." *European journal of nutrition* 58, no. 3 (2019): 1299-1313.
2. Yebyo, Henock G., Hélène E. Aschmann, and Milo A. Puhan. "Finding the balance between benefits and harms when using statins for primary prevention of cardiovascular disease: a modeling study." *Annals of internal medicine* 170, no. 1 (2019): 1-10.
3. Cooper, Cyrus. "Global, regional, and national burden of neurological disorders, 1990-2016: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2016." *The Lancet Neurology* 18, no. 4 (2019).
4. Fung, Jollee ST, Samuel Akech, Niranjan Kissoon, Matthew O. Wiens, Mike English, and J. Mark Ansermino. "Determining predictors of sepsis at triage among children under 5 years of age in resource-limited settings: A modified Delphi process." *PloS one* 14, no. 1 (2019).
5. Startin, Carla M., Sarah Hamburg, Rosalyn Hithersay, Tamara Al-Janabi, Kin Y. Mok, John Hardy, Andre Strydom et al. "Cognitive markers of preclinical and prodromal Alzheimer's disease in Down syndrome." *Alzheimer's & Dementia* 15, no. 2 (2019): 245-257.
6. Maul, J-T., A. A. Navarini, R. Sommer, F. Anzengruber, C. Sorbe, U. Mrowietz, M. Drach et al. "Gender and age significantly determine patient needs and treatment goals in psoriasis—a lesson for practice." *Journal of the European Academy of Dermatology and Venereology* 33, no. 4 (2019): 700-708.
7. Harrison, Theresa M., Renaud La Joie, Anne Maass, Suzanne L. Baker, Kaitlin Swinnerton, Laura Fenton, Taylor J. Mellinger et al. "Longitudinal tau accumulation and atrophy in aging and alzheimer disease." *Annals of Neurology* 85, no. 2 (2019): 229-240.
8. Afshin, Ashkan, Patrick John Sur, Kairsten A. Fay, Leslie Cornaby, Giannina Ferrara, Joseph S. Salama, Erin C. Mullany et al. "Health effects of dietary risks in 195 countries, 1990–2017: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2017." *The Lancet* 393, no. 10184 (2019): 1958-1972.
9. Theiss-Nyland, Katherine, Mila Shakya, Rachel Colin-Jones, Merryn Voysey, Nicola Smith, Abhilasha Karkey, Sabina Dongol et al. "Assessing the impact of a Vi-polysaccharide conjugate vaccine in preventing typhoid infections among Nepalese children: a protocol for a phase III, randomized control

- trial." *Clinical Infectious Diseases* 68, no. Supplement_2 (2019): S67-S73.
10. Chang, Angela Y., Vegard F. Skirbekk, Stefanos Tyrovolas, Nicholas J. Kassebaum, and Joseph L. Dieleman. "Measuring population ageing: an analysis of the Global Burden of Disease Study 2017." *The Lancet Public Health* 4, no. 3 (2019): e159-e167.
 11. Daly, Sinéad, Joon Seong, Robert Newcombe, Maria Davies, Julie Nicholson, Mark Edwards, and Nicola West. "A randomised clinical trial to determine the effect of a toothpaste containing enzymes and proteins on gum health over 3 months." *Journal of dentistry* 80 (2019): S26-S32.
 12. Mehta, Puja R., Ashley R. Jones, Sarah Opie-Martin, Aleksey Shatunov, Alfredo Iacoangeli, Ahmad Al Khleifat, Bradley N. Smith et al. "Younger age of onset in familial amyotrophic lateral sclerosis is a result of pathogenic gene variants, rather than ascertainment bias." *Journal of Neurology, Neurosurgery & Psychiatry* 90, no. 3 (2019): 268-271.
 13. Dupont, Pénélope Sévigny, Christian Bocti, Maude Joannette, Marie Maxime Lavallée, Jim Nikelski, Guillaume T. Vallet, Howard Chertkow, and Sven Joubert. "Amyloid burden and white matter hyperintensities mediate age-related cognitive differences." *Neurobiology of aging* 86 (2020): 16-26.
 14. Zaror, Carlos, Yolanda Pardo, Gerardo Espinoza-Espinoza, Àngels Pont, Patricia Muñoz-Millán, María José Martínez-Zapata, Gemma Vilagut et al. "Assessing oral health-related quality of life in children and adolescents: a systematic review and standardized comparison of available instruments." *Clinical oral investigations* 23, no. 1 (2019): 65-79.
 15. Anderson IV, John D., Karoun H. Bagamian, Farzana Muhib, Mirna P. Amaya, Lindsey A. Laytner, Thomas Wierzba, and Richard Rheingans. "Burden of enterotoxigenic *Escherichia coli* and shigella non-fatal diarrhoeal infections in 79 low-income and lower middle-income countries: a modelling analysis." *The Lancet Global Health* 7, no. 3 (2019): e321-e330.